

Review Article

Habitat, distribution, medicinal values & bioactive compounds of *Gloriosa superba* L. (Colchicaceae)

Bhagwati Prashad Sharma¹, Subodh Kumar Kandari², N Anil Kumar³, Swati⁴ and Kumari Sunita^{4*}

¹Department of Botany, Sidharth Government College, Nadaun, Himachal Pradesh, India

²Department of Botany, Omkarananda Sarashwati Government Degree College, Devprayag, Tehri Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India

³Department of Botany, SYTR Government Degree College, Madakasira, Sri Sathya Sai (affiliated to S. K. University, Ananthapuramu), Andhra Pradesh, India

⁴Department of Botany, Plant Physiology and PGPR Lab., Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

*Email-Id: ksunita78@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0052-7147>

DOI:

Article Details: Received: 2025-12-26 | Accepted: 2026-01-11 | Available online: 2026-01-14

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Abstract: *Gloriosa superba* L. is a medicinally important perennial climber widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions of Asia and Africa. Traditionally valued in indigenous and classical medicinal systems, the species is recognized for its therapeutic potential in treating inflammatory disorders, arthritis, gout, skin diseases, parasitic infections and certain chronic conditions. The plant is also a rich source of pharmacologically significant bioactive compounds, notably colchicine and gloriosine, which have established applications in modern medicine. Despite its wide geographical distribution and extensive ethnomedicinal use, natural populations of *G. superba* are increasingly threatened due to habitat loss and unsustainable harvesting practices. Present work comprehensively synthesizes the available literature on the habitat characteristics, geographical distribution, traditional medicinal uses and bioactive constituents of *G. superba*. Furthermore, it critically discusses current research findings, identifies major knowledge gaps and outlines future research directions emphasizing conservation, pharmacological validation and sustainable utilization of this valuable medicinal plant.

Keywords: Bioactive compounds, colchicine, ethnomedicine, medicinal plant

Introduction

Medicinal plants have served as the foundation of traditional healthcare systems for centuries and continue to play a crucial role in modern drug discovery (Yuan et al., 2016). A significant proportion of contemporary pharmaceuticals are either directly derived from plant sources or developed based on phytochemicals identified through ethnobotanical knowledge (Vaou et al., 2025). In many developing regions, plant-based medicines remain the primary means of healthcare due to their accessibility, affordability and cultural acceptance (Owusu et al., 2025). The renewed global interest in natural products has further emphasized the importance of systematically documenting medicinal plants and scientifically validating their therapeutic potential (Abdallah et al., 2023).

Plate 1: Vegetative parts of *Gloriosa superba*, a) Habitat, b) Leaves, c) Flower and d) Flower bud

Among the diverse medicinal flora, *Gloriosa superba* L. (Plate 1), a member of the family Colchicaceae, is recognized for its remarkable medicinal and pharmacological significance (Jana and Skekhawat, 2011; Sharma, 2023). The plant is a perennial climbing herb characterized by striking flowers and underground tubers rich in bioactive compounds (Regula, 2025). It has been widely incorporated into traditional medical systems, such as Ayurveda and Siddha, as well as various indigenous healing practices across Asia and Africa (Ashokkumar, 2015). Different parts of the plant, particularly the tubers and seeds, have been traditionally used to manage inflammatory conditions, musculoskeletal disorders, skin ailments and parasitic infections, reflecting a broad spectrum of ethnomedicinal applications (Pendharkar and Bagul, 2025). Overexploitation and unsustainable utilization have endangered the plant species in wild in many parts of India including Shivalik hills of Himachal Pradesh (Badola, 2002; Sharma, 2023), Odisha, Jharkhand, Tamil Nadu and Gujrat (Joshi et al., 2024). The therapeutic relevance of *G. superba* is largely attributed to its unique phytochemical composition, especially the presence of colchicine and related alkaloids (Pandey et al., 2021). Colchicine is a well-established anti-inflammatory and anti-mitotic agent with clinical applications in gout, arthritis, and certain genetic and neoplastic disorders (Dalbeth et al., 2014). This pharmacological importance has elevated *G. superba* from a traditionally valued plant to a species of global commercial interest (Balachandar et al., 2022). However, the same bioactive compounds that confer medicinal benefits also contribute to the plant's toxicity, necessitating careful dosage regulation and scientific validation of traditional formulations (Regula, 2025). Despite its wide distribution and medicinal prominence, *G. superba* faces increasing threats due to habitat loss, overharvesting and unsustainable exploitation driven by pharmaceutical demand (Chandrawanshi et al., 2013). Natural populations are declining in several regions, raising concerns about genetic erosion and the long-term availability of this species. In this context, a comprehensive understanding of its habitat, distribution, medicinal values and bioactive constituents is essential. Present study aims to synthesize existing knowledge on *G. superba*, highlighting research gaps and future directions for conservation and sustainable utilization.

Methodology

The present study is based on an extensive survey of published literature related to *Gloriosa superba*. Scientific databases, including Google Scholar, Scopus, PubMed, and Web of Science, were consulted to retrieve peer-reviewed research articles, review papers, ethnobotanical surveys and pharmacological studies. Keywords including “*Gloriosa superba*,” “medicinal uses,” “bioactive compounds,” “colchicine,” and “ethnopharmacology” were used to identify relevant publications. Additionally, regional floras, theses, books and reports documenting traditional knowledge and distribution patterns were examined. Only studies containing verifiable scientific or ethnomedicinal data were considered. Information obtained was critically analyzed and systematically organized under thematic sections to ensure clarity and coherence (Kumar, 2025).

Results and discussion

The literature study reveals that *Gloriosa superba* exhibits a broad ecological amplitude and geographical distribution. The species occurs naturally across India, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Malaysia,

Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Kenya and Bangladesh. Within India, it is distributed across diverse states including Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Haryana, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Chhattisgarh, Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Goa, Tamil Nadu, Jharkhand, Sikkim, Bihar, Uttarakhand and Punjab. The plant has also been reported from protected ecosystems such as the Pachmarhi Biosphere Reserve in Madhya Pradesh, indicating its ability to adapt to varied climatic and edaphic conditions. Ethnomedicinal evidence demonstrates that *G. superba* is used to treat rheumatism, gout, arthritis, chronic ulcers, piles, skin diseases, intestinal worm infestations and inflammatory disorders. Contemporary studies further highlight its anti-tumor, anticancer and immunomodulatory potential, as well as its application in managing Familial Mediterranean fever.

Table 1: Distribution of *Gloriosa superba*

Distribution	Source
India, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Malaysia, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa and Zambia In India: Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Haryana, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Chhattisgarh, Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Goa and Tamil Nadu	Umavathi et al., (2020); Regula, (2025)
Zimbabwe, South Africa, Tanzania and Kenya	Regula, (2025)
Bangladesh In India: Pachmarhi Biosphere Reserve, Madhya Pradesh	Khandel et al., (2012)
Jharkhand	Lal and Mishra, (2011)
Sikkim, Bihar, Uttarakhand and Punjab	Pandey et al., (2021)

Phytochemical investigations confirm the presence of major alkaloids such as colchicine and gloriosine, along with volatile constituents like 1-undecene. These compounds are primarily responsible for the plant's pharmacological activities and commercial importance.

Table 2: Medicinal uses of *Gloriosa superba*

Medicinal uses	Source
Anticancer properties	Kumar et al., (2025)

Anti-inflammatory and anti-tumor activity	Pandey et al., (2014)
Arthritis	Jana and Shekhawat, (2011)
Chronic ulcers	Cocco et al., (2010)
Familial Mediterranean fever	Goel et al., (2022)
Intestinal worms	Khanam et al., (2015)
Piles	Shen et al., (2011)
Rheumatism and gout	Jana and Shekhawat, (2011); Pandey et al., (2021)
Skin diseases	Pattarachotanant et al., (2024)
Wounds infested with maggots	Sharma et al., (2024)

Table 3: Bioactive compounds of *Gloriosa superba*

Bioactive compounds	Source
Colchicine	Pandey et al., (2021); Misra et al., (2017); Misra et al., (2021)
Gloriosine	Goel et al., (2022); Misra et al., (2017); Misra et al., (2021)
1-undecene	Kiros et al., (2023)

The wide distribution of *G. superba* across continents highlights its ecological adaptability; however, its medicinal value is closely linked to specific plant parts, particularly tubers and seeds, which are harvested destructively (Pandey et al., 2021). This has significant implications for population sustainability. The plant's ethnomedicinal applications strongly correlate with the biological activities of its bioactive compounds, especially colchicine, which exhibits anti-inflammatory, anti-mitotic and anticancer properties (Goel et al., 2022). Despite its therapeutic potential, the toxic nature of *G. superba* remains a critical concern. Improper dosage and unregulated use can result in severe poisoning, highlighting the importance of scientific validation and standardization (Premaratna et al., 2015). While pharmacological studies have validated some traditional claims, many medicinal uses remain supported only by ethnobotanical evidence. Moreover, most phytochemical studies focus predominantly on colchicine, leaving other potentially valuable compounds underexplored (Misra et al., 2021). The study emphasizes the need for balanced utilization strategies that integrate traditional knowledge with modern scientific frameworks.

Research gaps

Several critical research gaps persist in the study of *Gloriosa superba*. There is limited clinical evidence supporting many of its traditional medicinal applications. Toxicological studies addressing safe dosage ranges, long-term effects and drug interactions are inadequate. Furthermore, population-level ecological studies assessing genetic diversity, regeneration capacity and habitat-specific threats are scarce. From a phytochemical perspective, comprehensive profiling of secondary metabolites beyond well-known alkaloids remains insufficient. Additionally, standardized cultivation and propagation protocols are lacking, which hampers conservation and sustainable commercial exploitation.

Future aspects

Future research should prioritize multidisciplinary approaches combining ethnobotany, pharmacology, conservation biology and biotechnology. Development of sustainable cultivation techniques and tissue culture protocols could significantly reduce pressure on wild populations. Advanced analytical tools such as metabolomics and molecular docking studies may help identify novel bioactive compounds and therapeutic targets. Clinical trials and toxicological evaluations are essential to translate traditional knowledge into safe, evidence-based medicine. Policy-level interventions, community awareness programs and benefit-sharing mechanisms should also be promoted to ensure long-term conservation and equitable utilization of *G. superba*.

Conclusion

Gloriosa superba is a medicinally significant plant with extensive traditional applications and well-documented bioactive constituents. Its wide distribution and potent pharmacological properties highlight its importance in both traditional and modern medicine. However, increasing anthropogenic pressures, coupled with limited scientific validation and conservation measures, threaten its sustainability. Present study highlights the urgent need for integrated research and conservation strategies to safeguard this valuable medicinal resource while maximizing its therapeutic potential through scientifically validated and sustainable practices.

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